

Temperature dependence of the AB lines and optical properties of the carbon–antisite–vacancy pair in 4H-SiC

Oscar Bulancea-Lindvall ^{2,3,4}, Viktor Ivády,^{1,5,6}
Rickard Armiento ¹

¹Department of Physics, Chemistry and Biology (IFM), Linköping University, SE-58183 Linköping, Sweden

²HUN-REN Wigner Research Centre for Physics, P.O. Box 49, H-1525 Budapest, Hungary

³Department of Atomic Physics, Institute of Physics, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Műgyetem rakpart 3., H-1111 Budapest, Hungary

⁴MTA-WFK Lendület “Momentum” Semiconductor Nanostructures Research Group, P.O. Box 49, H-1525 Budapest, Hungary

⁵Department of Physics of Complex Systems, Eötvös Loránd University, Egyetem tér 1-3, H-1053 Budapest, Hungary

⁶MTA–ELTE Lendület “Momentum” NewQubit Research Group, Pázmány Péter, Sétány 1/A, 1117 Budapest, Hungary

(Received 18 December 2023; accepted 29 August 2024; published 24 September 2024)

Defects in semiconductors have in recent years been revealed to have interesting properties in the venture towards quantum technologies. In this regard, silicon carbide has shown great promise as a host for quantum defects. In particular, the ultrabright AB photoluminescence lines in 4H-SiC are observable at room temperature and have been proposed as a single-photon quantum emitter. These lines have previously been studied and assigned to the carbon–antisite–vacancy (CAV) pair. In this paper, we report on new measurements of the AB lines’ temperature dependence, and carry out an in-depth computational study on the optical properties of the CAV defect. We find that the CAV defect has the potential to exhibit several different zero-phonon luminescences with emissions in the near-infrared telecom band, in its neutral and positive charge states. However, our measurements show that the AB lines only consist of three nonthermally activated lines instead of the previously reported four lines; meanwhile, our calculations on the CAV defect are unable to find optical transitions in full agreement with the AB-line assignment. In light of our results, the identification of AB lines and the associated room-temperature emission require further study.

DOI: [10.1103/PhysRevApplied.22.034056](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevApplied.22.034056)

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum devices for information processing and communication will require fundamental components that are robust against noise and practical for efficient state manipulation and photon emission. Point defect qubits found in wide-band-gap semiconductors are promising candidates for such applications because of their substantial display of optical and spin properties, and their potential for localized spin states well isolated from decoherence sources [1–8]. Their capacity for single-photon emission is also

a vital ability for quantum information applications, e.g., communication and cryptography [9].

The nitrogen–vacancy (N–V) center in diamond has been leading the field among defects studied in the last decade, with demonstrated coherent control of its spin states and bright single-photon emission even under ambient conditions [4,10,11]. The success of this defect in various quantum device applications has invigorated the search for defects with similar or improved properties, including the consideration of new hosts with potential technological advantages. In particular, silicon carbide (SiC) that shares many of the relevant properties of diamond and can be found in a myriad of polytypes with capabilities to host numerous color centers is regarded as a promising alternative host [1,7,12–14]. Its established presence in industry has led to mature high-power electronics and advanced device fabrication techniques, which could prove to be an advantage in upcoming spin-photon applications [15,16].

*Contact author: oscar.bulancea.lindvall@liu.se

Published by the American Physical Society under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the published article’s title, journal citation, and DOI. Funded by [Bibsam](https://www.bibsam.com/).

Recent studies have showcased a number of interesting defects in SiC with promising abilities as near-telecom wavelength emitters and qubits with coherent lifetimes rivaling the N-V center [2,7,17–19]. Furthermore, measurements of the 4H- and 6H-SiC polytypes have shown that these hosts are the source of ultrabright photoluminescence [20], in the 640–680 nm range for 4H-SiC, emitting at a rate of Mcps [21]. Such a high brightness is rare for defects in bulk materials and has the potential to become a vital component in quantum optics with the significant enhancement of photonic nanocavities [15,16].

Observations of this emission at nitrogen temperature (80 K) have found that it consists of eight lines, dubbed A1–A4 and B1–B4 in order of increasing wavelength. Six of these lines (A1, A2, B1–B4) were studied and initially assigned to the neutral carbon–antisite–vacancy (CAV) pair in early works based on the available optical measurements [20,22]. The two remaining lines, A3 and A4, were later presented in the spectrum at 80 K in Castelletto *et al.* [21], who also reported *ab initio* calculations finding no visible-light photoluminescence for the neutral CAV state. Castelletto *et al.* [21] instead provided a reasonable model for how the eight lines could be assigned to the four configurations of the positively charged CAV defect (CAV⁺). The A2, A4, B2, and B4 lines were attributed to zero-phonon lines of the four nonequivalent defect configurations in 4H-SiC, whereas the A1, A3, B1, and B3 lines were suggested to originate from respective second split-off excited states, emerging due to a Jahn-Teller splitting of degenerate energy level pairs in the excited state, which are temperature activated at 80 K [21]. The spectrum was therefore reinterpreted as belonging to the positive charge state, pending a complete characterization of its excited state dynamics.

The assignment of the AB lines to the CAV⁺ defect has since been prominent in the field, leading to its use in studies of defect formation and fabrication. In particular, the AB lines have been used as markers for CAV defect formation and incorporated into models for defect conversion pathways [23]. The assignment has similarly been applied to ascertain the efficiency of CAV⁺ creation in micropillar fabrication and charge control via Schottky barrier diodes [24].

However, the spectra observed at 7 K in Ref. [20] display significant contributions from the B1 and B3 lines. This contribution should be weaker at 7 K in view of the also observed respective 4-meV separation from the B2 and B4 lines, suggesting that the observed contribution may be caused by local laser heating. Furthermore, while the temperature dependence for the B lines has been presented [20], the behavior of the A lines has not been investigated.

In the present work, we report on the complete temperature dependence of the spectrum that compels us to revisit the assignment of these lines to the CAV defect.

In addition, despite extensive knowledge of the structure and ground-state properties of the CAV defect showcased in previous works and the motivations behind the AB-line identification [21], its excited states and spin properties have yet to be explored by *ab initio* methods, taking into account all charge states and configurations. A thorough characterization for the CAV could contribute to the working model for the origin of the AB lines and reveal additional properties as a quantum emitter and qubit. Modern first-principle methods have proven their ability to provide accurate predictions of material properties, in particular for optical and spin properties of defects [25]. Therefore, this paper will also present a detailed first-principle characterization of the CAV defect, involving its optical and spin-related properties relevant for the previously highlighted areas of interest and provide data for comparison to the measurements on the AB lines at low temperatures. In particular, beyond what has previously been characterized, we give estimates for radiative lifetimes and polarizations of all calculated zero-phonon lines (ZPLs). In addition, we solve the Bethe-Salpeter equation [26] on top of a single-shot Green-function-based *GW* approximation (G_0W_0) [27] to the CAV⁺ system, which has previously only been considered for the neutral CAV state [17].

This paper is structured as follows. In Sec. II, we present the experimental setup and results of photoluminescence measurements on the AB lines. Then, in Sec. III, we provide a description and introduction to the CAV defect (Sec. III A), detail the first-principle characterization, starting with an introduction to the examined quantities and tools (Sec. III B), and present relevant results. In Sec. IV, we reflect on the relevance of the defect as a quantum emitter and its relation to the AB lines.

II. PHOTOLUMINESCENCE IN THE AB-LINE SPECTRUM

For measurement of the AB lines at low temperatures, we use a commercial high-purity semi-insulating (HPSI) 4H-SiC substrate that has been irradiated with 2-MeV electrons to a fluence of 10^{17} cm⁻². The substrate has the crystal *c* axis nearly perpendicular to the surface. The excitation laser wavelength used to obtain the photoluminescence (PL) spectra of the AB lines is 514.5 nm. The laser (about 15 mW in power) is moderately focused to a spot of about 2 mm in diameter at the sample to avoid local heating. The PL is excited through and collected from the edge of the sample, to ensure that light with both parallel and perpendicular polarizations to the *c* axis can be registered. The temperature dependence of the lines is measured in a liquid-He-operated cryostat with a temperature controller. The PL was registered using a double monochromator (SPEX 1404) equipped with GaAs-photocathode photomultiplier.

The AB-line spectrum is obtained at temperatures between 3.9 and 150 K (see Fig. 1), including the 80-K point that is presented in Ref. [21]. In the spectrum at 80 K (cf. the inset in Fig. 1), we can clearly see the eight lines A1–A4 and B1–B4 shown in Ref. [21] that have been proposed to be due to localized excitations in the positive charge state of the CAV [21,28]. In fact, the spectrum is nearly identical to that presented in Ref. [21].

The model of the CAV^+ defect predicts four PL lines, A2, A4, B2, and B4, originating from transitions to lowest-energy excited states in each of the four CAV^+ configurations in $4H$ -SiC. The remaining four lines, A1, A3, B1, and B3, are not observable at low (liquid helium, LHe) temperatures because the higher-energy counterparts of the excited states, split off by the Jahn-Teller effect, are not populated. Hence, the model predicts that the latter four lines will emerge at higher temperatures when the

higher-energy excited states become significantly populated (e.g., at 80 K used for the spectrum in Ref. [21]). The above notion can be easily checked if the temperature dependence of the spectrum is measured down to the LHe temperature, as displayed in Fig. 1.

We note that the experimental data are in conflict with the model suggested in Ref. [21]. Firstly, the B1 and B3 lines indeed vanish at the LHe temperature, and are thus associated with higher-energy excited states of the defects producing the ZPLs B2 and B4, respectively. However, the A2 and A4 lines also vanish, indicating that they cannot be ZPLs corresponding to transitions between a ground state and the corresponding lowest-energy excited state. Secondly, the A1 line is not a higher-energy counterpart of the A2 line because it does not vanish at LHe temperature. Thus, the low-temperature spectrum of the AB lines displays only three lines, A1, B2, and B4, instead of four corresponding to the number of CAV^+ configurations in $4H$ -SiC. Hence, the experimental data lead us to conclude that the CAV^+ model proposed in Ref. [21] does not correspond to the observed AB-line spectrum.

We note, however, that our results still support the notion that the lines are due to the same defect in different configurations. This can be asserted because of the intensity ratios between A1, B2, and B4 being consistently equal, which we have also observed in various other samples at low temperature (2–4 K).

FIG. 1. Temperature dependence of the AB lines in an HPSI $4H$ -SiC substrate obtained with 514.5-nm excitation under low-power density conditions ($< 0.5 \text{ W/cm}^2$). The insert focuses on the spectrum at 80 K, which is akin to the spectrum in Fig. 1(a) of Ref. [21]. Note that the low-temperature spectrum at 3.9 K (top curve) only exhibits the A1, B2, and B4 lines, whereas the A2, A3, A4 lines, similar to the B1 and B3 lines, only appear at higher temperatures and are most probably associated with higher excited states of the defect responsible for the B1–B4 PL lines.

III. FIRST-PRINCIPLE CHARACTERIZATION

A. The carbon–antisite–vacancy pair

The carbon–antisite–vacancy pair is an intrinsic defect in SiC, which may exist in four nonequivalent configurations, as illustrated in Fig. 2. It is stoichiometrically equivalent to the silicon vacancy, as they can be interchanged by the migration of a nearest-neighbor carbon of the silicon vacancy. This transformation is predicted to have an activation barrier of 1.9–2.7 eV and can be effectuated by annealing at temperatures of approximately

FIG. 2. Illustrations of the vacancy and carbon-antisite placements for the possible configurations of the CAV defect in $4H$ -SiC.

750 °C [29,30]. Two of its configurations have the carbon displacement axis parallel to the crystal c axis, which are usually denoted hh and kk because of the local hexagonal (h) and cubic (k) environment of both the carbon vacancy and the carbon antisite. These on-axis configurations exhibit C_{3v} symmetry, resulting in the appearance of an a_1 and a twice degenerate e one-electron state in the band gap, similar to that of the $N-V$ center in diamond [31]. The other configurations, denoted hk and kh (cf. Fig. 2), are off axis, meaning that they do not share the axial symmetry of the unit cell and therefore exhibit C_{1h} symmetry.

The effect of this lowered symmetry in the band structure can be understood as a splitting of the degenerate e state into corresponding a' and a'' states. Initial structural characterization identified the single positively charged and neutral state to be C_{3v} symmetric with an occupied local a_1 state and an unoccupied e state inside the band gap [32,33]. However, following *ab initio* studies found there to be a Jahn-Teller (JT) distortion taking place upon occupation of one of the e states, affecting the symmetry in certain charge states [17]. Specifically, the neutral charge state in the axial configurations was suggested to be more stable in a C_{1h} symmetrical configuration due to the JT effect. Similar observations were made for the negatively charged state, also occupying one of the otherwise degenerate e bands [32]. This implies the need for special care in characterizing level transitions, as a change in occupation could also accompany structural and behavioral changes in the electronic structure through the introduction or loss of the JT distortion. The hk and kh would not require such special treatment as these configurations already split the degenerate bands owing to their natural *per se* C_{1h} symmetry.

B. Computational methods

In this work, we calculate excited-state properties within the Kohn-Sham density functional theory, mainly using the method of constrained occupations [34]. To aid the identification of the defect-localized states, we also employ the measure known as the inverse participation ratio (IPR) [35] of a wave function ϕ ,

$$\text{IPR}(\phi) = \frac{\int_V |\phi|^4 d^3\vec{r}}{(\int_V |\phi|^2 d^3\vec{r})^2}, \quad (1)$$

where V denotes the supercell volume. This measure yields values within the interval $[1/V, 1]$, where its extreme values of $1/V$ and 1 are given for the special cases of a fully delocalized and a point-localized wave function, respectively, giving a reliable measure of the localization within these bounds.

Among the quantities we include in the optical characterization, we present the ZPLs of all characterized transitions, corresponding transitional dipole moments, and

radiative lifetimes. ZPLs are determined by the ΔSCF methodology [34], comparing the total energies of the states

$$E_{\text{ZPL}} = E_{\text{ex,tot}} - E_{\text{ground,tot}} + E_{\text{corr}}, \quad (2)$$

using the structurally relaxed total excited-state energy $E_{\text{ex,tot}}$ and ground-state energy $E_{\text{ground,tot}}$, with a possible correction, E_{corr} , due to finite-size and charge-interaction effects.

The two terms on the right-hand side of Eq. (2) provide an accurate description for transitions between localized defect states, when finite-size effects are effectively canceled out. Using the Heyd, Scuseria, and Ernzerhof exchange correlation functional (HSE06) [36], results have also been shown to agree with experimental measurements up to an error margin of approximately 0.1 eV [25].

However, transitions involving bound excitons in charged defect states require extra caution as the excited electron state may be particularly delocalized from the defect site. In these cases, an additional charge correction needs to be provided, to account for the effect of the charge jellium background in addition to the considerable delocalization of the electron state.

Popular model-based charge-correction schemes such as those by Freysoldt *et al.* [37], Makov and Payne [38], and Lany and Zunger [39] assume a charge model based on a localized defect charge density and are not likely to accurately incorporate the exciton in their descriptions. Describing an extended electron state with a local charge model could possibly be achieved by choosing a large effective Bohr radius, or by adjusting the charge of the center to fit the supercell-size scaling result. Both approaches are difficult to apply accurately without detailed knowledge of the scaling beforehand. For this reason, we instead investigate the supercell convergence behavior in order to estimate the size of the E_{corr} term. We limit this analysis to the case of the positive charge state of the hh configuration, under the assumption that the correction is largely independent of the actual atomic configuration of the CAV defect.

We estimate the radiative lifetime of the transitions according to [40]

$$\tau_{f,i} = \frac{3\epsilon_0 h^4 c^3}{2(2\pi)^3 n E_{f,i}^3 |\vec{\mu}_{f,i}|^2} \quad (3)$$

with $E_{f,i}$ the energy difference between the compared states, taken as E_{ZPL} in this work, n the refractive index of 4H-SiC, here chosen as $n = 2.6473$, and transitional dipole moments

$$\vec{\mu}_{f,i} = \langle \phi_f | e\vec{r} | \phi_i \rangle, \quad (4)$$

where ϕ_f and ϕ_i are the final and initial electronic wave functions of the transition. While this element should

ideally be evaluated using the many-body wave functions of the defect states, they are here approximated by the Kohn-Sham orbitals involved in the transition. Such a simplification is nontrivial, but has been shown for native defects in SiC to reproduce polarizations observed in experiments and provide quantitative agreement with measured lifetimes, with optimal accuracy for the case of using final and initial states taken from the relaxed geometries of respective excited and ground states [41].

As an alternative approach to the above methods of optical characterization, we additionally apply single-shot GW calculations (G_0W_0) [27], adding the quasiparticle correction to the defect levels, and solve the Bethe-Salpeter equation (BSE) [26] to more accurately describe the screening in the electron-hole interaction of bound-to-free transitions. With these methods, we obtain the dielectric function of the relevant CAV states that we relate to the absorption spectrum. This technique has previously been applied to the carbon vacancy in SiC to include strong excitonic effects in the photoionization process, demonstrating an ability to predict excitation thresholds [42].

In the first-principle characterization, we employ highly accurate density functional theory (DFT) calculations as implemented in the Vienna *Ab initio* Simulation Package (VASP) [43,44] using the projector-augmented-wave method. Calculations are performed in a 576-atom supercell containing a single CAV center, using the hybrid HSE06 functional [36] at the Γ point, with a 420-eV plane-wave cutoff. For high convergence, a 10^{-6} - and 5×10^{-5} -eV limit is applied for the respective density and structural relaxations. For practical considerations of the constrained occupation calculations in VASP, see the [Appendix](#).

Hyperfine and zero-field splitting (ZFS) parameters are obtained under the same settings, but using Γ -point Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) Kohn-Sham orbitals for the ZFS. This is done as a postprocessing step using the methods presented in Refs. [45,46] as implemented in VASP.

G_0W_0 VASP calculations were performed on top of the HSE06-converged structure and wave functions of a 256-atom supercell, using more than 10 times as many unoccupied bands as occupied and applying a GW energy cutoff of 200 eV. The BSE calculation is done on top of the GW

FIG. 3. The band structure and ZPL energies of the respective possible transition for the CAV hh and kk configurations, showing the double positive (a),(e), positive (b),(f), neutral (c),(g), and negative (d),(h) charge states. ZPL values are displayed in electronvolts, with blue arrows free-to-bound transitions, red arrows bound-to-free transitions, and green arrows fully localized transitions. One should note that the positive states display two local transitions, varying in energy due to the JT relaxation that occurs after excitation onto the degenerate states.

FIG. 4. The band structure and ZPL energies of the respective possible transition for the CAV hk and kh configurations, showing the double positive (a),(e), positive (b),(f), neutral (c),(g), and negative (d),(h) charge states. ZPL values are displayed in electronvolts, with blue arrows free-to-bound transitions, red arrows bound-to-free transitions, and green arrows fully localized transitions. The reader should note the observable splitting in the positive state, yielding varying differences in ZPLs between the transitions $a'_C \rightarrow a'_{Si}$ and $a'_C \rightarrow a''_{Si}$ on the size of 0.04 and 0.3 eV for the respective hk and kh cases.

solution, including 100 electron-hole pairs, which, by the resulting GW quasiparticle energies, should account for transitions up to 4 eV above gap.

C. Characterization results

The defect ground states and their respective Kohn-Sham band structures are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 for the on-axis hh and kk configurations and the off-axis hk and kh configurations, respectively. As presented, the charge states considered in this study are the neutral (CAV⁰) state in an $S = 1$ triplet state, the positive (CAV⁺) state in an $S = 1/2$ spin state, the double positive (CAV⁺⁺) state with $S = 0$, and the negative (CAV⁻) state with $S = 1/2$. However, the neutral ground state may in fact form either a triplet or a spin singlet state, which respectively exhibit C_{1h} and C_{3v} structural symmetries. In this work, the singlet state is not considered for an optical characterization, as we have found the triplet state to be more energetically favorable, in agreement with other works [17], with an energy separation of about 0.3 eV. Alternative spin states for the other charge states are not found in this study.

Out of the four dangling bonds of the CAV, one is found to be deep in the valence band (not shown in Figs. 3 and 4), roughly 0.9 eV below the valence band edge, while the other three states are typically found inside the band gap. This varies among the various charge states, as the Jahn-Teller splitting may cause the highest-lying dangling bond to rise into the conduction band. This is true for the neutral and negative charge states, for which the two defect states

FIG. 5. Defect Kohn-Sham states of the hh CAV⁺, with the $a_1(a'_C)$ state (a) and the two $e(a'_{Si})$ and $e(a''_{Si})$ states (b),(c) respectively. Plotted with the package for visualization for electronic and structural analysis (VESTA) [47].

TABLE I. Properties of the studied excitations in the CAV^+ state, showing the ZPL, radiative lifetime, and dipole moment as calculated from first principles, categorized by the exhibiting ground state. Transitions are labeled by the resulting hole and occupied state, discerning between the two a' states formed from the a_1 and e states under symmetry breaking by the localization around the carbon ($a_1 = a'_C$) or the vacancy-neighboring silicon (e , or a'_{Si} and a''_{Si}). CBM, conduction-band minimum; VBM, valence-band maximum.

<i>hh</i>					<i>kk</i>				
Transition	ZPL (eV)	Lifetime (μ s)	$ \vec{\mu}_{xy} $ (D)	$ \vec{\mu}_z $ (D)	Transition	ZPL (eV)	Lifetime (μ s)	$ \vec{\mu}_{xy} $ (D)	$ \vec{\mu}_z $ (D)
$a_1 \rightarrow$ CBM	1.55	0.32	0.00	1.40	$a_1 \rightarrow$ CBM	1.47	1.06	0.82	0.03
$a_1 \rightarrow e$	0.94	1.12	1.56	0.01	$a_1 \rightarrow e$	0.85	1.75	1.47	0.02
$a_1 \rightarrow e$	0.94	1.12	1.56	0.00	$a_1 \rightarrow e$	0.84	1.82	1.45	0.01
VBM $\rightarrow e$	3.04	1.66	0.22	0.01	VBM $\rightarrow e$	2.32	4.52	0.13	0.16
VBM $\rightarrow a_1$	2.67	3.34	0.09	0.00	VBM $\rightarrow a_1$	2.61	15.70	0.05	0.08
<i>kh</i>					<i>hk</i>				
Transition	ZPL (eV)	Lifetime (μ s)	$ \vec{\mu}_{xy} $ (D)	$ \vec{\mu}_z $ (D)	Transition	ZPL (eV)	Lifetime (μ s)	$ \vec{\mu}_{xy} $ (D)	$ \vec{\mu}_z $ (D)
$a'_C \rightarrow$ CBM	1.43	1.87	0.64	0.13	$a'_C \rightarrow$ CBM	1.47	1.02	0.78	0.31
$a'_C \rightarrow a''_{Si}$	0.83	0.33	3.47	0.40	$a'_C \rightarrow a'_{Si}$	0.56	0.34	4.41	4.43
$a'_C \rightarrow a'_{Si}$	0.50	2.40	1.28	1.44	$a'_C \rightarrow a''_{Si}$	0.60	0.29	5.98	0.04
VBM $\rightarrow a'_{Si}$	2.19	1.36	0.40	0.00	VBM $\rightarrow a'_{Si}$	2.27	28.3	0.08	0.00
VBM $\rightarrow a'_C$	2.20	3.01	0.27	0.00	VBM $\rightarrow a'_C$	2.29	35.6	0.07	0.00

that end up in the band gap display a' character, with the exception of the hk neutral charge state where the higher-lying state in the gap is of a'' representation. In charge states where the JT splitting does not take place, the states are found within the gap with a_1 and degenerate e state characters where C_{3v} symmetry applies.

Among these three states, the a_1 (a') state, which is in all cases lower lying, is more localized on the antisite carbon atom [see Fig. 5(a)] and the e (a' and a'') states are gathered in proximity to the neighboring silicon atoms of the vacant carbon [see Figs. 5(b) and 5(c)]. To provide a unique identifier to these states in the lower symmetry cases, the carbon-localized state will hereafter be denoted by a'_C and the others by a'_{Si} and a''_{Si} .

As seen in Figs. 3 and 4, the excitations considered in this paper are the lowest possible bound-to-free and free-to-bound transitions as well as excitations between localized states, as indicated by the IPR measure. In this sense, only the smallest transitions from (to) the valence (conduction) band are considered due to the proximity in energy to the known ionization levels. Bound-to-bound transitions involving states inside the valence and conduction bands are in most cases excluded for the same reason or lack of stability in the convergence.

Out of the transitions resulting from these considerations, we make special note of the bound-to-bound transitions in the CAV^+ state denoted by $a'_C \rightarrow a'_{Si}$ and $a'_C \rightarrow a''_{Si}$, as a possible origin of the AB lines. These excitations are here seen to create two transitions in each configuration, due to the splitting of the degenerate e states upon occupation. However, it should be noted that there is some difficulty in converging the $a_1 \rightarrow e(a'_{Si})$ transition

in HSE06, possibly due to the state mixing that could occur between the a'_C and a'_{Si} states because of their similar characters during the JT distortion. These particular transitions are therefore in the hh and kk configurations, calculated while enforcing the ground-state symmetry, thus preventing the JT splitting and resulting in what may be seen as an upper bound for the ZPL. These local transitions can be seen in Table I to be strictly polarized as $E \perp c$ in the $a_1 \rightarrow e$ states, while less strictly constrained in the cases of the $a'_C \rightarrow a'_{Si}$ and $a'_C \rightarrow a''_{Si}$ transitions in the off-axis configurations, in accordance with selection rules of respective C_{3v} and C_{1h} symmetries [21].

These transitions yielded ZPL energies at 0.94, 0.85, 0.83, and 0.60 eV for the hh , kk , kh , and hk configurations, respectively, with respective lifetimes for the $a'_C \rightarrow a''_{Si}$ of 1.12, 1.75, 0.329, and 0.287 μ s. The calculated ZPL energies thus differ substantially from the AB lines at 1.8–1.9 eV. The transitions that could match the AB lines in the CAV^+ state are the exciton states obtained from $a'_C \rightarrow$ CBM transitions. Such bound exciton transitions can also fit into the proposed working model, given that they exhibit the same group theoretical characteristics the model is based on, giving rise to similar polarization properties and reasonably small separation to the next excited state. These transitions are found to be 1.55, 1.47, 1.47, and 1.43 eV for the hh , kk , hk , and kh configurations with respective radiative lifetimes of 0.32, 1.1, 1.0, and 1.9 μ s. The polarization of these transitions are also calculated as mainly $E \perp c$, except in the hh configuration.

One can note that these ZPLs have a significant difference of about 0.35 eV from the observed line energy seen in Fig. 1 at 3.9 K. This may in part be because of finite-size

effects caused by the delocalization of the exciton state and an insufficient description of the electron-hole interaction. Larger supercell calculations up to about 4600 atoms at the PBE level do show a trend of increasing ZPL, but do not indicate a correction much larger than 0.1 eV (see the Supplemental Material [48]). The reader may also note that the excitations discussed thus far have generally been shown to have relatively long lifetimes. None of those presented for the positive charge state are likely to agree with the experimentally estimated lifetime of about 1 ns [21].

A $GW + BSE$ calculation on the kk configuration yields the absorption spectrum shown in Fig. 6. The defect-local transition is too weak to be discernible in the spectrum, in agreement with the predicted long lifetimes, but is found at roughly 1.33 eV. The strongest peak in this range is attributed to the lowest bound-to-free transition, found at 1.56 eV, in proximity to the predicted ZPL. We therefore see that the correction of the electron-hole interaction does not significantly increase the ZPL prediction, but rather sets an upper bound on the transition energy still well below the expected AB-line energy.

Interestingly, however, there are three additional contributions appearing at 1.64, 1.77, and 2.20 eV, which all involve the excitation to higher conduction-band states, revealing possibly complex excitation properties of the defect. The two peaks higher in energy are not as easily dismissed as candidates for the AB lines based on energy arguments.

In the neutral charge state, we find bound exciton transitions in $a'_{Si} \rightarrow CBM$ (except for hk , with $a''_{Si} \rightarrow CBM$)

FIG. 6. The $G_0W_0 + BSE$ absorption spectra of the kk CAV^+ state, discerned by either parallel or perpendicular polarization. The y axis shows the imaginary component of the obtained dielectric function, which is proportional to the absorption coefficient of the system. Arrows point to transitions involving the defect. Note that the defect-local transition $a_1 \rightarrow e$ is marked although its oscillator strength is too low to be observed in the spectrum. Here $a_1 \rightarrow CBM+$ denotes transitions from the defect to above-CBM bands.

FIG. 7. Averaged hyperfine parameters of the CAV^+ state at C_{Si} compared to corresponding experimental findings for the various defect configurations, showing quantitative agreement with the experimental findings of Umeda *et al.* [33], within an approximately 15% margin of error.

in the 0.81–0.95 eV range, as has been predicted in earlier work [17], but here we also report on the radiative lifetimes being of the order of 1 μ s and above, with a polarization mainly perpendicular to the c axis with the exception of the kh configuration. For details, see the Supplemental Material [48]. Other defect transitions do not yield ZPL values that are clearly below the limit of ionization and were also not successfully converged in the kh configuration due to the difficulty in capturing the local states within the conduction band. We do however obtain a 1.16-eV ZPL with a noteworthy radiative lifetime of 30 ns in the kk configuration.

Hyperfine parameters of the antisite carbon are found to have one distinct value along the defect axis, and two nearly identical parameters perpendicular to this axis due to the defect symmetry. These values are in the respective ranges of 117–249 and 26–59 MHz for CAV^0 , and 245–286 and 57–93 MHz for CAV^- , except the hh configuration that displays hyperfine parameters of about 1 MHz in the CAV^- case. In Fig. 7, the values for CAV^+ are presented alongside experimental reference values from Ref. [33], for which one finds agreement within a 15% relative margin of error and close to full agreement in the principal axis directions (full disclosure is detailed in the Supplemental Material [48]). Hyperfine calculations for the silicon and carbon neighbors yield values in the range 1–40 MHz.

TABLE II. Zero-field splitting parameters of the neutral CAV triplet ground state.

Configuration	D (GHz)	$ E $ (MHz)
hh	−1.92	568
kk	−2.17	684
hk	−1.70	12
kh	−2.07	356

Only the neutral charge state has more than one unpaired spin in its ground state, producing a zero-field splitting. This is calculated to what is shown in Table II. The triplet ground state yields an axial component D in the approximate -2 -GHz range and a nonzero transversal E component varying within the range 300–700 MHz with the exception of the hk configuration at an order of 10 MHz.

IV. DISCUSSION

Starting with the ground-state properties, Kohn-Sham band structures and wave-function characteristics are in good agreement with what has previously been reported in other studies of the CAV [17,21,32]. We find the hyperfine parameters for the positively charged state in excellent agreement with the measurements carried out by Umeda *et al.* [33] up to the accuracy expected from HSE06 at the Γ point [45]. Because of both this qualitative and quantitative agreement with our results, we are confident that the studied states are the physically formed defect ground states.

Our results also indicate that the CAV defect is able to produce transitions in the 1550-nm (about 0.8-eV) range suitable for fiber-optical applications. This implies its possible use as a single-photon emitter in quantum communication networks and optics-based quantum information processing [49] and sensing technologies [50], facilitating the use of existing fiber-optics systems with minimal signal attenuation. Other defects, such as the diamond $N-V$ center, require wavelength conversion of their emission to match the desired wavelengths, which can reduce the signal-to-noise ratio by orders of magnitude [51]. Furthermore, association of the excitation with manipulable and long-lived ground-state spin of $S = 1$ and $S = 1/2$, for the neutral and positive charge states, respectively, would make the defect applicable as a spin-photon interface acting as a memory node within quantum networks to allow for long-range transmission with reduced signal loss.

Starting with the neutral charge state, this was predicted for the bound-to-free excitations calculated in previous works [17]. However, our findings on the radiative lifetimes indicate that they may not be particularly bright, but sufficiently long lived for manipulation of the produced exciton state. In contrast, the neutral state of the kk configurations is found to host a localized transition and shows a promisingly small lifetime of just 30 ns at a ZPL of 1.16 eV. However, the ZPL lies on the border of the $(0|+)$ ionization threshold [17], and illumination at the necessary wavelength may instead photoionize the defect to the positive state and hinder the observation of this emission.

The positive charge state also holds local state transitions that are predicted to fall in the optimal near-infrared range. The axially symmetric configurations yield ZPLs of 0.85–0.95 eV, although we note that we could not fully

relax the hh excited state to achieve the correct symmetry. Therefore, the approximate 0.95-eV values may further reduce closer to the ideal 0.8-eV reference. We take special note of the positive kh configuration that shows potential for a 0.83-eV ZPL in the $a'_C \rightarrow a''_{Si}$ transition that also exhibits the lowest radiative lifetime. The lifetime of 0.3 μ s is still considered high in comparison to that of other well-known SiC defects, e.g., the silicon vacancy [52] or divacancy [53], of the order of 10 ns. However, in the context of spin-photon interfaces, even defects such as the T center in silicon, exhibiting an even longer radiative lifetime (0.94 μ s), have garnered attention as possible spin-photon interfaces by leveraging their emission in the telecom O band (1326 nm, 0.935 eV), high collection efficiency in the ZPL, and their inherent spin dynamics [54]. The CAV defect and this specific telecom emission warrant further studies to explore the applicability in quantum optical devices.

The negative and double positive states do not have luminescence in the near-infrared. This was expected for the negative state due to its ionization threshold of approximately $E_C - 0.5$ eV [17], while we show in this work that the discernibly lowest transitions in the double positive state correspond to 1.6 eV. These transitions are in the range of the predicted ionization levels or higher, meaning that the charge states are likely limited to these excitations for observable luminescence. One may finally note that the lifetimes calculated for the double positive and negative states are of the order of 1 μ s or larger, implicating a low brightness.

In regards to the AB lines, our measurements at low temperatures reveal that the nonthermally activated lines consist of three, rather than four, lines. Furthermore, lines A2, A3, and A4, together with lines B1 and B3 must all be high-temperature lines. It is quite certain that the B1 and B3 lines are related to higher excited states of the defects responsible for the appearance of the B2 and B4 lines, in agreement with Ref. [21]. However, it is also possible that the A2, A3, and A4 lines are higher excited states related to the B2 and B4 lines, suggesting a more complicated structure of the excited state than the two-level splitting from an e state (in C_{3v}) into a' and a'' states (in C_{1h} symmetry). The currently accepted CAV⁺ model cannot explain these experimental observations.

Likewise, there is an absence of predicted transitions in the 1.8–1.9-eV range of the AB-line spectrum. Transitions between localized defect states are here evaluated to lie below about 1 eV, while the bound-to-free transitions, after taking possible supercell-size effects into account, lie 0.2–0.3 eV below the AB lines. Improving the accuracy of the electron-hole interaction via $GW + BSE$ calculations does not significantly alter this prediction. In light of the calculated radiative lifetimes, it is also uncertain if these transitions could produce the brightness observed at room temperature, of the order of Mcounts per second [21].

The $GW + BSE$ absorption spectrum, however, includes several transitions to higher conduction-band states, forming possible excitons with an increased likelihood to agree with the AB-line energies, particularly the states found at 1.77 and 2.20 eV in Fig. 6. Attributing the AB lines to any of these above-CBM states would also be in line with the observed blinking of the AB-line luminescence with low-wavelength lasers [21], which could then be attributed to photoionization in the already delocalized electron-hole state. However, we note that these above-CBM transitions are mainly polarized in $E \parallel c$, and the AB lines, particularly the B2 and B4 lines, are efficiently excited by $E \perp c$ polarized light. Furthermore, these transitions involve nondegenerate states that should not exhibit a dynamical JT splitting, and therefore do not yield an apparent explanation for the appearance of line pairs in the on-axis configurations.

Moreover, considering developments in the optical charge state control of the CAV, measured by electron paramagnetic resonance [55], our results for the lowest bound-to-free transition are in good agreement with the onset of quenching in the positive state population. In contrast, at illumination energies of the AB lines (1.8 eV) and above, the CAV^+ population is shown to already suffer considerable quenching [55].

Unfortunately, one does not find suitable alternatives among the other charge states of this defect. The free-to-bound transitions $VBM \rightarrow a_1(a'_c)$ in the double-positive states might be possible candidates in terms of the ZPL, but fall short when considering the calculated lifetimes, which are even longer than those found for the single-positive state. Considering a different charge state than the positive would also imply abandoning the trends in annealing of the AB lines observed in the earlier work of Steeds [22] and more recent confirmations [56]. These associate the disappearance of the lines related to the silicon vacancy due to annealing, with an increase of the AB lines, which could imply a small energy barrier between the silicon vacancy and the responsible defect, which has been shown for the positive CAV state [17]. Our results thus open the model up for new interpretations in terms of the optical properties of the associated defect.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we examined the temperature dependence of the AB photoluminescence lines at low temperatures and performed a detailed theoretical characterization of the CAV defect in $4H$ -SiC, covering optical and spin properties. We found that the AB-line spectrum, in contrast to reports at 80 K, consists of three lines at 649 (A1), 673 (B2), and 677 nm (B4) at 3.9 K, and that the other lines must come from excited states that are thermally activated. Our theoretical investigations on the CAV defect found spin properties, e.g., hyperfine strength and ZFS,

in good agreement with experimental findings and predictions in previous works, and revealed optical transitions in the infrared belonging to the CAV^+ and CAV^0 states.

However, our characterization of the CAV defect was unable to conclude a matching set of zero-phonon lines that would suit the AB lines. In combination with our findings on the low-temperature behavior of the spectrum, the identification of the AB lines requires reinterpretation and further studies.

While transitions predicted in previous works, such as the bound-to-free transition in the CAV^0 state, are here calculated to have relatively low radiative rates, we find higher rates among the bound-to-bound transitions of the defect. The above-gap defect band of the CAV^0 state features exceptionally low lifetime. However, to ensure its photostability, further studies into the photoionization of the CAV^0 state and the presence of this emission would be of interest.

The CAV^+ is shown to host telecom emission of high interest for quantum optical technologies. This is most relevant for the off-axis configurations where the radiative lifetimes are the lowest and one transition is close to the telecom C band.

Furthermore, the BSE spectra calculated in this work indicate several above-CBM excitations available for the CAV^+ state below its predicted ionization energy, which could imply more complex excitation dynamics than previously predicted.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We acknowledge support from the Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation through the WBSQD project (Grant No. 2018.0071). I.G.I. acknowledges support from the Swedish Research Council (Grant No. VR 2016-05362). Support from the Swedish Government Strategic Research Area SeRC and the Swedish Government Strategic Research Area in Materials Science on Functional Materials at Linköping University (Faculty Grant SFO-Mat-LiU No. 2009 00971) is gratefully acknowledged. V.I. was supported by the National Research, Development, and Innovation Office of Hungary via the Quantum Information National Laboratory of Hungary (Grant No. 2022-2.1.1-NL-2022-00004) and under Grant No. FK 145395. The computations were enabled by resources provided by the National Academic Infrastructure for Supercomputing in Sweden (NAISS) and the Swedish National Infrastructure for Computing (SNIC) at NSC partially funded by the Swedish Research Council through Grant Agreements No. 2022-06725 and No. 2018-05973. We acknowledge the EuroHPC Joint Undertaking for awarding project access to the EuroHPC supercomputer LUMI, hosted by CSC (Finland) and the LUMI consortium through a EuroHPC Regular Access call.

A.G. acknowledges the National Office of Research, Development, and Innovation of Hungary (NKFIH) Grant No. KKP129866 of the National Excellence Program of Quantum-coherent materials project, the support for the Quantum Information National Laboratory from the Ministry of Culture and Innovation of Hungary (NKFIH Grant No. 2022-2.1.1-NL-2022-00004), projects SPINUS (Grant No. 101135699), and the EU Horizon project QuMicro (Grant No. 101046911).

APPENDIX: CONSTRAINED OCCUPATION CALCULATIONS WITH HYBRID FUNCTIONALS USING VASP

Our theoretical characterization of excited states uses constrained occupation DFT, as described in Sec. III B. In this approach, one explicitly sets the occupation of the one-electron Kohn-Sham orbitals according to a given orbital order and calculates the corresponding state under this restriction. However, one must ensure that the desired states remain occupied throughout the calculation. Hence, it is necessary to prevent the reordering of orbitals when seeking the excited-state electron density.

Excited-state calculations with hybrid functionals are particularly prone to reordering the orbitals since the exact-exchange term generally lowers the energy of occupied states and increases it for unoccupied states. If the orbitals are allowed to reorder, the calculation may either not converge or end in an unintended final state. This can also happen if one does not have a predefined orbital ordering at the start of the calculation. It is therefore preferable to start from a precreated WAVECAR and turn off explicit eigenstate diagonalization with `LDIAG = FALSE`.

In calculations using the VASP software, the `FERWE` and `FERDO` input parameters restrict the orbitals to occupy. However, for such calculations, the resulting behavior of the input parameters needed to keep the orbitals from reordering differ between versions of VASP. In VASP 5.4.1 (and possibly earlier versions), if the calculation is started with a precreated WAVECAR file (`ISTART = 1`) and preventing state-space diagonalization, the desired result is achieved when using the damped velocity friction algorithm (`ALGO = Damped`). However, the use of other algorithms changes the behavior of the subspace rotations for this kind of calculation, which prevents it from converging into the desired final state. Furthermore, later VASP versions (5.4.4, 6.2.0, and 6.2.1) change the settings for `ALGO = Damped` so that the subspace rotations behave the same way as for the other `ALGO` settings.

We have found how to modify the VASP source code so that the change in subspace rotations can be avoided under these conditions for all relevant `ALGO` choices and earlier versions. We are happy to share these changes with others working with similar calculations in these earlier versions. After reaching out to the VASP developers on this

matter, the corresponding change was implemented as of version 6.3.0.

- [1] J. R. Weber, W. F. Koehl, J. B. Varley, A. Janotti, B. B. Buckley, C. G. Van De Walle, and D. D. Awschalom, Quantum computing with defects, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. USA* **107**, 8513 (2010).
- [2] W. F. Koehl, B. B. Buckley, F. J. Heremans, G. Calusine, and D. D. Awschalom, Room temperature coherent control of defect spin qubits in silicon carbide, *Nature* **479**, 84 (2011).
- [3] T. D. Ladd, F. Jelezko, R. Laflamme, Y. Nakamura, C. Monroe, and J. L. O'Brien, Quantum computers, *Nature* **464**, 45 (2010).
- [4] M. W. Doherty, N. B. Manson, P. Delaney, F. Jelezko, J. Wrachtrup, and L. C. Hollenberg, The nitrogen-vacancy colour centre in diamond, *Phys. Rep.* **528**, 1 (2013).
- [5] F.-F. Yan, J.-F. Wang, Q. Li, Z.-D. Cheng, J.-M. Cui, W.-Z. Liu, J.-S. Xu, C.-F. Li, and G.-C. Guo, Coherent control of defect spins in silicon carbide above 550 K, *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **10**, 044042 (2018).
- [6] N. T. Son, C. P. Anderson, A. Bourassa, K. C. Miao, C. Babin, M. Widmann, M. Niethammer, J. Ul Hassan, N. Morioka, I. G. Ivanov, F. Kaiser, J. Wrachtrup, and D. D. Awschalom, Developing silicon carbide for quantum spintronics, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **116**, 190501 (2020).
- [7] S. Castelletto, T. Katkus, and S. Juodkazis, in *SPIE Micro + Nano Materials, Devices, and Applications 2019*, edited by M. C. Simpson and S. Juodkazis (SPIE, Melbourne, Australia, 2019), p. 38..
- [8] D. D. Awschalom, L. C. Bassett, A. S. Dzurak, E. L. Hu, and J. R. Petta, Quantum spintronics: Engineering and manipulating atom-like spins in semiconductors, *Science* **339**, 1174 (2013).
- [9] G. Brassard, N. Lütkenhaus, T. Mor, and B. C. Sanders, Limitations on practical quantum cryptography, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **85**, 1330 (2000).
- [10] C. Kurtsiefer, S. Mayer, P. Zarda, and H. Weinfurter, Stable solid-state source of single photons, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **85**, 290 (2000).
- [11] P. L. Stanwix, L. M. Pham, J. R. Maze, D. Le Sage, T. K. Yeung, P. Cappellaro, P. R. Hemmer, A. Yacoby, M. D. Lukin, and R. L. Walsworth, Coherence of nitrogen-vacancy electronic spin ensembles in diamond, *Phys. Rev. B* **82**, 201201(R) (2010).
- [12] A. L. Falk, B. B. Buckley, G. Calusine, W. F. Koehl, V. V. Dobrovitski, A. Politi, C. A. Zorman, P. X.-L. Feng, and D. D. Awschalom, Polytype control of spin qubits in silicon carbide, *Nat. Commun.* **4**, 1819 (2013).
- [13] L. Gordon, A. Janotti, and C. G. Van De Walle, Defects as qubits in 3C- and 4H-SiC, *Phys. Rev. B* **92**, 045208 (2015).
- [14] A. Lohrmann, B. C. Johnson, J. C. McCallum, and S. Castelletto, A review on single photon sources in silicon carbide, *Rep. Prog. Phys.* **80**, 034502 (2017).
- [15] S. Yamada, B.-S. Song, T. Asano, and S. Noda, Silicon carbide-based photonic crystal nanocavities for ultra-broadband operation from infrared to visible wavelengths, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **99**, 201102 (2011).

- [16] D. M. Lukin, M. A. Guidry, and J. Vučković, Integrated quantum photonics with silicon carbide: Challenges and prospects, *PRX Quantum* **1**, 020102 (2020).
- [17] K. Szász, V. Ivády, I. A. Abrikosov, E. Janzén, M. Bockstedte, and A. Gali, Spin and photophysics of carbon-antisite vacancy defect in 4H silicon carbide: A potential quantum bit, *Phys. Rev. B* **91**, 121201(R) (2015).
- [18] B. Magnusson, N. T. Son, A. Csóré, A. Gällström, T. Ohshima, A. Gali, and I. G. Ivanov, Excitation properties of the divacancy in 4H-SiC, *Phys. Rev. B* **98**, 195202 (2018).
- [19] K. C. Miao, J. P. Blanton, C. P. Anderson, A. Bourassa, A. L. Crook, G. Wolfowicz, H. Abe, T. Ohshima, and D. D. Awschalom, Universal coherence protection in a solid-state spin qubit, *Science* **369**, 1493 (2020).
- [20] J. W. Steeds, Photoluminescence study of the carbon antisite-vacancy pair in 4H- and 6H-SiC, *Phys. Rev. B* **80**, 245202 (2009).
- [21] S. Castelletto, B. C. Johnson, V. Ivády, N. Stavrias, T. Umeda, A. Gali, and T. Ohshima, A silicon carbide room-temperature single-photon source, *Nat. Mater.* **13**, 151 (2014).
- [22] J. Steeds, G. Evans, L. Danks, S. Furkert, W. Voegeli, M. Ismail, and F. Carosella, Transmission electron microscope radiation damage of 4H and 6H SiC studied by photoluminescence spectroscopy, *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **11**, 1923 (2002).
- [23] R. Karsthof, M. E. Bathen, A. Galeckas, and L. Vines, Conversion pathways of primary defects by annealing in proton-irradiated *n*-type 4H-SiC, *Phys. Rev. B* **102**, 184111 (2020).
- [24] M. E. Bathen, G. M. Selnesaunet, M. J. Enga, S. B. Kjeldby, J. Müting, L. Vines, and U. Grossner, Charge state control over point defects in SiC devices, *Defect Diffusion Forum* **425**, 35 (2023).
- [25] P. Deák, B. Aradi, T. Frauenheim, E. Janzén, and A. Gali, Accurate defect levels obtained from the HSE06 range-separated hybrid functional, *Phys. Rev. B* **81**, 153203 (2010).
- [26] M. Rohlfing and S. G. Louie, Electron-hole excitations and optical spectra from first principles, *Phys. Rev. B* **62**, 4927 (2000).
- [27] L. Hedin, New method for calculating the one-particle Green's function with application to the electron-gas problem, *Phys. Rev.* **139**, A796 (1965).
- [28] S. Castelletto, L. Rosa, and B. C. Johnson, in *Advanced Silicon Carbide Devices and Processing*, edited by S. E. Saddow and F. La Via (InTech, Rijeka, Croatia, 2015).
- [29] M. Bockstedte, A. Mattausch, and O. Pankratov, *Ab Initio* study of the annealing of vacancies and interstitials in cubic SiC: Vacancy-interstitial recombination and aggregation of carbon interstitials, *Phys. Rev. B* **69**, 235202 (2004).
- [30] E. Rauls, Th. Lingner, Z. Hajnal, S. Greulich-Weber, Th. Frauenheim, and J.-M. Spaeth, Metastability of the neutral silicon vacancy in 4H-SiC, *Phys. Status Solidi (b)* **217**, r1 (2000).
- [31] Á. Gali, *Ab Initio* theory of the nitrogen-vacancy center in diamond, *Nanophotonics* **8**, 1907 (2019).
- [32] T. Umeda, N. T. Son, J. Isoya, E. Janzén, T. Ohshima, N. Morishita, H. Itoh, A. Gali, and M. Bockstedte, Identification of the carbon antisite-vacancy pair in 4H-SiC, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **96**, 145501 (2006).
- [33] T. Umeda, J. Isoya, T. Ohshima, N. Morishita, H. Itoh, and A. Gali, Identification of positively charged carbon antisite-vacancy pairs in 4H-SiC, *Phys. Rev. B* **75**, 245202 (2007).
- [34] A. Gali, E. Janzén, P. Deák, G. Kresse, and E. Kaxiras, Theory of spin-conserving excitation of the $N - V^-$ center in diamond, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **103**, 186404 (2009).
- [35] C. Pashartian and O. Rubel, Localization of electronic states in III-V semiconductor alloys: A comparative study, *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **7**, 064011 (2017).
- [36] J. Heyd, G. E. Scuseria, and M. Ernzerhof, Hybrid functionals based on a screened Coulomb potential, *J. Chem. Phys.* **118**, 8207 (2003).
- [37] C. Freysoldt, J. Neugebauer, and C. G. Van De Walle, Fully *ab initio* finite-size corrections for charged-defect supercell calculations, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **102**, 016402 (2009).
- [38] G. Makov and M. C. Payne, Periodic boundary conditions in *ab initio* calculations, *Phys. Rev. B* **51**, 4014 (1995).
- [39] S. Lany and A. Zunger, Assessment of correction methods for the band-gap problem and for finite-size effects in supercell defect calculations: Case studies for ZnO and GaAs, *Phys. Rev. B* **78**, 235104 (2008).
- [40] A. M. Stoneham, *Theory of Defects in Solids: Electronic Structure of Defects in Insulators and Semiconductors* (Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2001), Chap. 10.
- [41] J. Davidsson, Theoretical polarization of zero phonon lines in point defects, *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **32**, 385502 (2020).
- [42] M. Bockstedte, A. Marini, O. Pankratov, and A. Rubio, Many-body effects in the excitation spectrum of a defect in SiC, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **105**, 026401 (2010).
- [43] G. Kresse and J. Hafner, *Ab Initio* molecular-dynamics simulation of the liquid-metal–amorphous-semiconductor transition in germanium, *Phys. Rev. B* **49**, 14251 (1994).
- [44] G. Kresse and J. Furthmüller, Efficient iterative schemes for *ab initio* total-energy calculations using a plane-wave basis set, *Phys. Rev. B* **54**, 11169 (1996).
- [45] K. Szász, T. Hornos, M. Marsman, and A. Gali, Hyperfine coupling of point defects in semiconductors by hybrid density functional calculations: The role of core spin polarization, *Phys. Rev. B* **88**, 075202 (2013).
- [46] V. Ivády, T. Simon, J. R. Maze, I. A. Abrikosov, and A. Gali, Pressure and temperature dependence of the zero-field splitting in the ground state of NV centers in diamond: A first-principles study, *Phys. Rev. B* **90**, 235205 (2014).
- [47] K. Momma and F. Izumi, *VESTA 3* for three-dimensional visualization of crystal, volumetric and morphology data, *J. Appl. Crystal.* **44**, 1272 (2011).
- [48] See Supplemental Material at <http://link.aps.org/supplemental/10.1103/PhysRevApplied.22.034056> for a detailed description of the optical characterization of the CAV defect in all considered states and configurations, the calculated hyperfine strength of the CAV⁺ doublet, the defect-to-band ZPL scaling with supercell size, and a full account of the *GW*+BSE spectra for additional configurations.

- [49] E. Knill, R. Laflamme, and G. J. Milburn, A scheme for efficient quantum computation with linear optics, *Nature* **409**, 46 (2001).
- [50] M. Müller, H. Vural, C. Schneider, A. Rastelli, O. G. Schmidt, S. Höfling, and P. Michler, Quantum-dot single-photon sources for entanglement enhanced interferometry, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **118**, 257402 (2017).
- [51] A. Dréau, A. Tchebotareva, A. E. Mahdaoui, C. Bonato, and R. Hanson, Quantum frequency conversion of single photons from a nitrogen-vacancy center in diamond to telecommunication wavelengths, *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **9**, 064031 (2018).
- [52] R. Nagy, M. Widmann, M. Niethammer, D. B. R. Dasari, I. Gerhardt, Ö. O. Soykal, M. Radulaski, T. Ohshima, J. Vučković, N. T. Son, I. G. Ivanov, S. E. Economou, C. Bonato, S.-Y. Lee, and J. Wrachtrup, Quantum properties of dichroic silicon vacancies in silicon carbide, *Phys. Rev. Appl.* **9**, 034022 (2018).
- [53] A. L. Falk, P. V. Klimov, B. B. Buckley, V. Ivády, I. A. Abrikosov, G. Calusine, W. F. Koehl, Á. Gali, and D. D. Awschalom, Electrically and mechanically tunable electron spins in silicon carbide color centers, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **112**, 187601 (2014).
- [54] L. Bergeron, C. Chartrand, A. T. K. Kurkjian, K. J. Morse, H. Riemann, N. V. Abrosimov, P. Becker, H.-J. Pohl, M. L. W. Thewalt, and S. Simmons, Silicon-integrated telecommunications photon-spin interface, *PRX Quantum* **1**, 020301 (2020).
- [55] N. T. Son, P. Stenberg, V. Jokubavicius, H. Abe, T. Ohshima, J. Ul Hassan, and I. G. Ivanov, Energy levels and charge state control of the carbon antisite-vacancy defect in 4H-SiC, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **114**, 212105 (2019).
- [56] R. Karsthof, M. E. Bathen, A. Galeckas, and L. Vines, Conversion pathways of primary defects by annealing in proton-irradiated *n*-type 4H-SiC, *Phys. Rev. B* **102**, 184111 (2020).